

State Versus Dynamic Variables, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics Part 3

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In Part 2, we argued that one should consider an equation of numbers describing the interaction variables of a free particle and their related independent features. In particular, we argued that these interaction variables are E , p_x , p_y and p_z and all are independent in the sense that E is linked with the distance a particle moves in a field while p_x , p_y and p_z are proportional to impulses in the y - z , x - z and x - y planes. Thus, a number equation must contain E , p_x , p_y and p_z , but demonstrate their independence. We argued for $-E dt + (p_x) dx + (p_y) dy + (p_z) dz$ ((1)), where $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$. We note, however, here that such an equation shows no geometry in the problem. We also argue that this geometry is linked with a trajectory.

We note that the approach of Part 2 applies to any E , p free motion system, in other words, equally well to a photon and particle with rest mass. In Part I, we noted that $E dt$ with $dt = \hbar/E$ could apply to $E = m_0 c^2$, where m_0 is a rest mass, but in such a case, $p_x \rightarrow 0$, $p_y \rightarrow 0$ and $p_z \rightarrow 0$ so $-E dt + (p_x) dx + (p_y) dy + (p_z) dz$ is the same as ((1)) for a photon and particle with rest mass. In other words, the quantum form $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ holds equally well for photons and particles with rest mass as it is based solely on the notion of p and E as interaction variables. In other words, there is no notion of spin in Part 2.

In this note, we wish to consider then, how the notion of spin arises and why it does not appear in the E , p_x, p_y, p_z analysis of Part 2. We suggest that spin appears if one considers geometries linked to trajectories, i.e. $-Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y + (p_z)z$ where x, y, z are not points on a trajectory as well as independence of E , m_0 , p_x , p_y , p_z . In other words, the independence of interaction variables used in Part 2 still applies, but one now introduces the extra feature of geometry to find spin. Thus, one has spin in addition to \hbar/E , \hbar/p_i .

The two approaches, however, have differences as one has, in a rest frame for a particle with rest mass, $-Et$ (no p presence) while for a photon, $-Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y + (p_z)z$. Thus, expressed in terms of a Lorentz invariant using trajectory x, y, z values one can distinguish between photons and particles with rest mass. Using the Lorentz invariant, $-EE + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0 c^2 c^2$, only E , p and m_0 appear, but again one may distinguish between a photon and particle with rest mass because $m_0 = 0$ for a photon. If one considers the notion of motion (trajectory) and Lorentz invariants, one is led to the notion of spin, as we argue. If on the other hand, as in Part 2, one only considers E and p_x, p_y, p_z as the interaction variables, and one wishes to have them independent, then one sees no spin and find ((1)). In other words, spin appears from comparing special relativistic states (ones viewed from frames moving with constant $-v$), i.e. ones with geometry as well as independence, instead of the more general view of Part 2 in which one considers all free E , p objects as representing one general number ((1)).

Argument of Part 2

The general argument of Part 2 was that one should create a number equation linking all free particles through E and (p_x, p_y, p_z) . In other words, these are considered to be the interaction variables of interest and it is stressed that all of them represent independent interactions. For instance, E is linked to the distance traveled in a field (or for a photon heat), while p_x , p_y and p_z

are proportional to impulse hits against z-y, x-z and y-x planes. In order to describe the independence, Part 2 relinquishes the notion of p_x, p_y, p_z taken as a dot product with a vector (i.e. $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$) and rather introduces a nonvector: $\hbar/p_x, \hbar/p_y$ and \hbar/p_z . This creates identical (π) \hbar/p_i units together with E/\hbar indicating that one has independent terms linked to interaction. This implies that $E/\hbar, \hbar/p(i)$ must also be linked with interactions. Part 2 suggested that these represent dt, dx, dy, dz because the sense of position is the only 3-component object left after the vector \mathbf{p} and one cannot use the vector \mathbf{r} as it does create independence, although it does create rotational invariant $\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ and Lorentz invariance with $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$.

Photon Versus Particle with Rest Mass

The above discussion focuses only E and the vector \mathbf{p} and so in principle should apply to both a photon and particle with rest mass. In fact, the approach:

$$-E/\hbar + p_x \hbar/p_x + p_y \hbar/p_y + p_z \hbar/p_z \quad ((1))$$

applies equally well to both. We note that this means that in the rest frame of a particle with rest mass m_0 , one has:

$$p_i \rightarrow 0, \text{ but } \hbar/p_i \rightarrow 1 \quad ((2))$$

The zero value of each p_i is erased so to speak by \hbar/p_i in this approach. Equating all free E, \mathbf{p} means that the rest frame is no longer special as it is in special relativity meaning that it does not distinguish between a photon and a particle with rest mass. We argue that this gives rise to a very general expression: $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ for both a photon and particle with rest mass as a kind of complex probability, i.e. a quantum feature.

This, however, begs the question: Photons do not have a rest mass and so is there a quantum feature which distinguishes between the two? In particular, it is known that photons have a quantum spin of 1 and spin $1/2$ particles a quantum spin of $1/2$, yet this does not seem to arise from ((1)).

The Sense of Spin

Dirac obtained spin $1/2$ quantum features by considering the Lorentz invariant:

$$-E^2 + c^2 \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((3))$$

with $E \rightarrow i \hbar \partial/\partial t$ and $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow -\hbar \nabla$

In this case, a rest frame is distinguished because for a photon the RHS is 0, while for a particle with rest mass, it is not. Dirac's approach was to assume a quantum form for E and \mathbf{p} , namely $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ as already existing. We suggest that this form follows from ((1)). Dirac's approach was to linearize ((3)) which means that the LHS contains the interaction variables $E,$

p_x, p_y, p_z , while the RHS only contains m_0 because $p_x=p_y=p_z=0$. The quantum mechanical approach associated with $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, however, considers $p_x=p_y=p_z=0$ as relevant information because it combines with $\pi \hbar/\pi = 1$.

To see this more clearly, one may consider a second Lorentz invariant which also holds, namely:

$$-Et' + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}' = -m_0 t \quad ((4))$$

In this case, $p_x=p_y=p_z=0$ does not appear on the RHS because one uses the trajectory vector (x,y,z) . This vector has finite components and so the product $\pi x_i = 0$ because $\pi_i=0$. In Part 2, we argued that this does not demonstrate the independence of p_x, p_y, p_z and so ((2)) and $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ follow from ((2)) instead.

((4)), however, is a less general invariance than ((1)) which equates all free objects. ((4)) is associated with special relativity and distinguishes between a rest mass and a 0 rest mass (photon). It does, however, by considering trajectory motion as well as a certain geometry $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ and independence of \mathbf{p} vector and E as well as p_x, p_y and p_z . This suggests that spin is linked with trajectory motion and geometry and the presence or absence of a rest mass, we argue. As a result, spin $\frac{1}{2}$ formalism emerges when one must consider explicitly linking a frame with E, \mathbf{p} to one with a rest mass (with $p=0$ meaning on \mathbf{p} term remains unlike ((1))), with the assumption of $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ already existing. This suggests that $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ follows from more general assumptions than those used for finding spin.

In particular, Dirac linearizes a Klein-Gordon equation, obtained from replacing E with $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and \mathbf{p} with $-i \nabla$ partial in ((4)) and having these operate on $\exp(-iEt+i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$. This leads to 4×4 matrices multiplied by E and π_i , with the matrices multiplied by π_i containing the 2×2 Pauli matrices. The 2×2 Pauli matrices ensure that π_i is only associated with π_i (i.e. $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$), while the 4×4 matrices are needed to ensure that E and m_0 are independent of each other and the π_i 's. Thus, geometry (from the dot product), trajectory (from the fact that $p_x=0$ in the rest frame) and independence of E, m_0 and p_x, p_y, p_z are all essential, we argue.

This result, however, only holds for the $m_0 \neq 0$ case and so is specific to being able to distinguish between a rest frame and a non-rest frame. This means that $p=0$ is unique in the rest frame, something that is not a consideration for ((1)) which treats all E and \mathbf{p} vectors as equivalent.

Photon Considerations

For $m_0=0$, there exists a completely different spin, namely spin 1, and one uses the Levi-Civita symbol, ϵ_{ijk} , which follows from Maxwell's equations which use $\mathbf{E} + i \mathbf{B}$ as the wavefunction, where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are the magnetic field. \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} , however, are perpendicular and exist in a plane perpendicular to \mathbf{p} . They have a $r-t$ dependence of $\cos(-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but this, in fact, follows again from a more general equation, namely a classical wave-equation, for \mathbf{E} (vector) and \mathbf{B} (vector) which does not contain spin. As a result, spin is a quantum feature that seems to follow from more restricted equations, namely ones which deal with trajectories and geometry, but at the same with independence of the \mathbf{p} vector and E , energy.

In the photon case, one may write various equations. The first is:

$$E = |p|c \quad ((5))$$

This is a number equation which bypasses the vector components of $|p|$ as only the magnitude of p matters, while the ignored p_x , p_y and p_z have physical implications, i.e. are proportional to impulse hits on two dimensional targets. As a result, we suggest that ((5)) does not contain enough information about interactions. One remedy is to use ((1)) which leads to $dt = \hbar/E$, $dx = \hbar/p_x$, $dy = \hbar/p_y$ and $dz = \hbar/p_z$. This approach, however, bypasses some of the geometry in the system which is directly linked to a trajectory.

A second set of equations which apply to the photon are:

$$1/c \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } X_i + \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} X_i = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Here $X_i = E_i$ or B_i

((6)) leads directly to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ (or more generally to $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$). This is the same result as ((1)), but the arguments of ((1)) have not been directly used. Again, no trajectory information or geometry (dot products, cross products) appears (and so this gives no information about spin.) We note that E_i and B_i are linked to certain kinds of interactions e.g. $q_1 E$ and $q_1 v \times B$, where q_1 is a test charge moving with a velocity v (vector). These two forces are expressed in terms of E (energy) and p vector if one uses $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$, but E and p are linked with different kinds of interactions. In particular, E is linked to heat for a photon and p is linked to impulse. Thus, E_i and B_i , linked to certain kinds of interactions, are written in terms of two different kinds of interactions E and p . p , however, is a vector while E is a number. Furthermore, there is an independence between E and p and in fact between p_x , p_y , p_z . Thus, the same arguments which seemed to apply to ((1)) seem to appear again here in order to write $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ when expressing E_i and B_i . The E_i and B_i interaction variables are directly linked to the E and p vector ones which means one must respect the independence of E , p_x , p_y , p_z .

A third equation which applies to a photon is:

$$\frac{d}{dt} (.5\epsilon_0 E_i \cdot E_i + .5/\mu_0 B_i \cdot B_i) + 1/\mu_0 \text{grad} \cdot (E_i \times B_i) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

This time, E_i and B_i are used to create energy density (first term on the LHS) and momentum density (second term on the RHS). In other words this is the reverse of ((6)) which expresses E_i and B_i in terms of E and p . As ((7)) stands, one sees a trajectory as $E_i \times B_i$ describes the direction of the motion of the photon. Geometry is present in the sense of dot and cross products. It also shows independence of energy and momentum, but one does not directly see any spin features.

Formally, to find spin from ((7)), one writes an equation in terms of $E_i + iB_i$ which removes geometrical constraints in ((7)). For example, the energy density term contains a dot product and the momentum density, a cross product. If one wishes to put ((7)) in the same form as ((6)), i.e. only show E_i and B_i , then the geometry constraints appear, i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} (E_i + iB_i) (i) + 1/\mu_0 \epsilon_{ijk} \frac{d}{dx_j} (E_i + iB_i) (k) = 0 \quad ((8))$$

In ((8)), one sees the emergence of spin as e_{ijk} is a spin matrix for spin 1. (i) represents the label of the spin matrix and j, k are its entries. Thus, spin emerges from displaying particular interaction variables, here E and B (and not dot and cross products), yet the underlying geometry and independence of E and p (vector) must be retained.

In the case of a particle with rest mass, a similar feature arises, namely one considers $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4$, but linearizes to obtain the interaction variables E, p . One must, however, show the geometry in the system as expressed by $p \cdot p$ as well as the independence of E, m_0 and p vector. This leads to Dirac's 4x4 matrices.

If one is not interested in the geometry in the system, then one may only focus on the independence of E, p_x, p_y and p_z and this yields $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$.

We note that equations which consider trajectories and geometry are less general than ((1)) which bypasses these features. In the examples, considered here the spin related equations are also linked to special relativity which equates different constant $-v$ frames whereas ((1)) equates all free moving particles with a p vector and E and does not single out a rest frame as being special, while special relativity does.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that two different kinds of analysis apply to spin and the quantum intervals: $dt = \hbar/E$, $dx_i = \hbar/p_i$ results. The latter is based on stressing the independence of E, p_x, p_y and p_z as interaction variables without considering any geometry in the problem (dot or cross products). In particular, E represents a certain kind of interaction (namely how far a particle with rest mass moves in a field or heat for a photon, and p_x, p_y, p_z are impulses against the y - z , x - z and z - y planes.)

This approach applies both to a photon and a particle with rest mass. In the case of a photon, one may also apply a wave equation to E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) independently. This, however, leads to one expressing E and B in terms of E and a p vector which again must be shown to be independent (including the independence of p_x, p_y, p_z). As a result, we argue that $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ applies in both approaches

In order to find spin, one must use a different type of equation, namely one which demonstrates geometry. This geometry is linked with a trajectory and geometry, we argue. As a result, in the $\hbar/E, \hbar/p_i$ approach, one considers $-m_0^2 c^4 + p \cdot p$ in the rest frame with $p \rightarrow 0$ and $dx = \hbar/p \rightarrow \infty$. In other words, $p=0$ does not mean that the p term disappears. In the case of a trajectory, x is finite so $-Et + px$ for $p=0$ means $px=0$. Thus, an equation which displays spin does not show a p term in the rest frame for a particle with rest mass. Thus, it is the Klein-Gordon equation (which already makes use of $\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r)$ as arising from different arguments) and linearizes it to display the interaction variables E, p, m_0 , but also display geometry in addition the independence of E, p_x, p_y, p_z, m_0 . Independence of variables is a feature of both spin and $\hbar/E, \hbar/p_i$ approaches, but spin relies on demonstrating geometry. In the case of a photon, this again applies because one uses a continuity equation with geometrical terms of $E \cdot E, B \cdot B$ and $E \times B$. When one linearizes to obtain the interaction variables E and B , the geometric features cannot disappear and so one sees the spin matrix e_{ijk} .